

AN IMPROVED SHEAR-LAG MODEL FOR NEEDLE-PUNCHED CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The damage of planar filaments by needle-punching is inevitable during the forming process of C/C composite preform. Hence, the stress concentration resulting from the needle-punching effect is a fundamental issue in the longitudinal strength model for needle-punched C/C composite laminates. The shear-lag models can give an analytical solution for the stress distribution and simplify the calculation. Current models assume an ordered distribution and don't include matrix stiffness. An improved shear-lag model has been proposed for assessing the stress concentration. In the present work, the matrix stiffness is introduced in the shear-lag model, and the finite difference method was combined to obtain the stress distribution with random needle-punched areas. The numerical solution shows a higher accuracy to predict the stress concentration factor. This enhanced model is then used to understand true stress transferring mechanism of needle-punched C/C composite laminates. Significant differences in the stress concentration are found by the assessment of three characteristic parameters (the overload length, the ineffective length and the maximum stress concentration factor). It is concluded that the stress concentrations caused by the ordered distribution of needle-punched areas is more obvious than random distribution. For an accurate representation of the stress concentration, random needle distributions in the needle-board should be used. The subject of future work is to create a strength model for the needle-punched C/C composite.

1 Introduction

Needle-punched C/C composites have been widely applied as rocket engine and aero brakes due to the high interlaminar strength, flexibility in making complicated crafts and relatively low cost [1, 2]. The damage of planar filaments by needle-punching is inevitable during the forming process of C/C composite preform [3, 4]. Local stress concentration occurs due to the broken fibers, which is similar to the failure model of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites.

The damage mechanism of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites has been studied in detail [5, 6]. The weakest fibers tend to fail first and lose load-transfer capability. Thus the surrounding fibers have to carry more load and the area over which the stress is increased is called the overload area. Besides the broken fibers recover their stress as the matrix transfer the load back to them and the area over which this occurs is called the ineffective area. The variation of the stress is quantified by the stress concentration factor (SCF), which is the relative variation according to the average stress far away from the broken fibers. The SCF distribution is crucial to predict the strength of unidirectional composites and has become a hotspot.

The initial stress concentration of needle-punched composite is weakened by the filling of carbon matrix, but it shares the same distribution characters with the failure model of unidirectional composites. A fundamental understanding of the initial stress concentration is also no doubt useful as it can improve the overall performance and help in designing better components. The calculation of the stress distribution can be divided into two approaches: finite element model (FEM) [7, 8] and shear-lag model (SLM) [9-12]. The distribution of needle-punching positions is indeed random. Therefore, SCF distribution should be approached in a statistical manner. FEM is computationally intensive and limited to a restricted zone. SLM is developed to calculate this stress distribution, however, the accuracy of SLM is not enough to predict an authentic SCF distribution.

In the present work, the matrix stiffness is introduced in the SLM. The stress distribution is obtained combining SLM with finite difference method. The FEM result is provided to verify the accuracy of the combining method. It will be illustrated that SCF distribution depends on the type of needle arrangement. Finally, an available suggestion is also given to optimize the needle-punching craft.

2 Description of the model

2.1 Numerical implementation

Under the assumption of shear-lag analysis, the tensile force in the n -th fiber is related to the displacement by

$$p_n(n) = EA \frac{du_n(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where EA is the extensional stiffness of the fibers, $u_n(x)$ is the displacement of the n -th fiber along the fiber direction.

The shear force, $s_n(x)$, per unit length between two adjacent fibers is also related to the displacement by

$$S_n(x) = \frac{G}{d} [u_{n+1}(x) - u_n(x)] \quad (2)$$

where G is the shear modulus of the cell and d is the effective fiber spacing.

By integrating Eq. (1) with Eq. (2), the equilibrium equation can be written as

$$EA \frac{d^2 u_n(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{G}{d} [u_{n+1} - 2u_n + u_{n-1}] = 0 \quad (3)$$

Based on the equilibrium equation, the finite difference method is used for numerical discretization. Figure 1 shows a part of needle-punched C/C composite laminate. The whole laminate is divided into small regions by dotted lines. Every region is an element in the difference grid. Like a unit cell, every element is composed of the fiber and matrix with the same shape. Based on the equilibrium equation, the relationship between an element and the adjacent four elements can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & (E_f d_f + E_m d_m) \frac{u_n(x + \Delta x) - 2u_n(x) + u_n(x - \Delta x)}{\Delta x^2} \\ & + \frac{2G_m G_f}{(G_f d_f + E_m d_m)} [u_{n+1}(x) - 2u_n(x) + u_{n-1}(x)] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where E_f is the fiber tensile modulus, G_f is the fiber shear modulus, d_f is fiber diameter, E_m is the matrix tensile modulus, G_m is the matrix shear modulus and d_m is the fiber spacing.

Figure 1: Discretization of a needle-punched C/C composite laminate

The above equation is the governing equation for the finite difference method. As far as the needle-punched area, there is only matrix in the element, so the fiber item is removed from the equation. Then the governing equation is applied to each element and equation systems are established implicitly. The uniform loading boundary is applied to the both end of the fibers. Traction free boundary conditions are applied to the lateral edge. Accordingly, the equation systems can be solved by the bi-conjugate gradient method. Typical mechanical properties of the composite can be found in Table 1.

Fiber stiffness	E/GPa	230
Fiber poisson's ratio		0.2
Matrix stiffness	E/GPa	20
Matrix poisson's ratio		0.3
Fiber Diameter	D/ μm	8
Effective fiber spacing	d/ μm	2

Table 1: Parameters of the combining method model

Finally, the necessary data are extracted out of the stress field. The SCF is calculated as the ratio of the location stress to the fiber stress far away from the needle-punching location. The ineffective area is defined as the area where SCF ranges from 0 to 0.9 and the overloaded area is defined as the area where SCF is higher than 1.1.

2.2 Method verification

To verify whether the combining method is accurate enough, the FEM result is provided based on Abaqus. The entire top edge is displaced vertically with a strain of 0.0005%. To avoid the impact on the result from the shear locking, quadratic elements are chosen in the FEM analysis. Figure 2 shows the stress concentration of a needle-punching laminate with a five-fiber breakage. The peak stress of the FEM result is 1.407 and the peak stress in the present work is 1.337. This is because each element calculated by the combining method is the average of lateral elements in a fiber calculated by FEM. The average stress of the eight lateral elements is 1.298. This means the combining method can be used with an acceptable reliability and validity.

Figure 2: Contour maps of the FEM result

3 Results and discussion

This section examines the influence of the needle-punching distributions. An ordered needle-

punching distribution is compared to five random distributions. Assume that there are five needle-punched areas with ten broken fibers in a $450\mu\text{m} \times 450\mu\text{m}$ plane for all the cases. This is a realistic needle-punching density inside needle-punched laminates. Three characteristic parameters of the SCF field is extracted out to assess the distribution (the overload area, the ineffective area and the max SCF).

Figure 3 shows the SCF field with the ordered distribution. There are a needle-punched area at each of the four corners, and the last area is placed in the center of the plane. The two overload areas in the middle of the place is affected by the adjacent area. A stress concentration banding is formed but it is not significant. Meanwhile few influence of the ineffective area on each other can be found. This is due to the long distance between two ineffective areas.

Figure 3: Contour maps of the ordered needle-punching distribution

As far as the five models with random needle-punching distribution, it is also necessary to keep the must distance ($30\mu\text{m}$) from each other. The statistical calculation is introduced for comparative analysis. Figure 4 shows the statistical results for the different distributions: single values for the ordered distribution, and average values with standard deviation for the random distribution. The random distribution have a much smaller overload area in size, while it get a larger ineffective area. These differences are due to the difference size of overload and ineffective area around a single needle-punched position. In the random models, some needle-punching area may be closer to another one. The overlaying effect will be more obvious than the ordered model. As we can see in Figure 3, the ineffective area is much bigger than the overload area around the same needle-punched position. This larger ineffective area leads to a far more significant effect. Hence, when an overload area is close to an ineffective area, SCF in this area will decrease. Besides, two close ineffective areas will have a stack effect inevitably. Meanwhile the distance between two overload areas is long enough that an overload area almost can't influence one another. Above all, the stress concentration degree is reduced in the random model.

Figure 4: Statistical results for the different distributions

4 Conclusion

Based on SLM, the finite difference method was used to obtain the stress distribution with random needle-punched areas. The numerical solution shows a higher accuracy to predict the stress concentration factor. This enhanced model is then used to understand true stress transferring mechanism of needle-punched C/C composite laminates.

Compared to the ordered distribution, significant differences in the stress concentration are found. The overload area is decreased, while the ineffective area is increased. It is concluded that the stress concentrations caused by the ordered distribution of needle-punched areas is more obvious than random distribution.

For an accurate representation of the stress concentration, random needle distributions in the needle-board should be used. The subject of future work is to create a strength model for the needle-punched C/C composite laminate.

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